

**EVALUATION OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE FREE
IRRIGATION SERVICE ACT (R.A. 10969)
IN NUEVA VIZCAYA**

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Evaluation of the Implementation of the Free Irrigation Service Act (R.A. 10969) in Nueva Vizcaya

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Abstract

The Republic Act No. 10969 was constructed and implemented to offer free irrigation to the farmers, including the condonation of their debts and backlogs. Hence, this study evaluated the implementation of the said program in terms of its operation and maintenance, its benefits and technical assistance to the Irrigators' Association, issues and concerns regarding FISA (Free Irrigation Service Act), and the recommended strategies to improve the program. The respondents were the farmers of the National Irrigation System of Colocol consisting of Bayombong, Villaverde, and Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. The research was qualitative and a descriptive-evaluative design that used a Likert Scale and Key Informant Interview (KII). As a result, the implementation of the FISA was very beneficial. According to the KII, farmers were satisfied with the program because of the free irrigation, some areas of the program however needed to be advanced and enhanced, mostly in the Operation & Maintenance (O&M) Section and Institutional Development Unit (IDU) of NIA.

Keywords: *evaluation, institutional development unit, irrigation, operation and maintenance, strategic plan*

Introduction

Agriculture is known as the art and science of nurturing the soil, growing crops, and raising livestock. Agriculture is also known for the preparation of plants and animal products for people's usage and also for market purposes (National Geographic, N.D.). Agriculture can produce many things that are viable to us humans, such as foods, fabrics, wood for construction, paper products, and many more to mention. Thus providing us the most of the world's basic needs. Many developing agricultural-producing countries depend on agriculture imports and food certainty, and many emerging countries will not refine without a significant increase in local production. It is evident that for the last few years, the role of Agriculture in world economic development has gone through important progress.

As one aspect to consider in Agriculture, irrigation plays a huge role not just in increasing the crops but also in reducing viability in production through improved control of the crop environment. A study, "Impact of irrigation on production and income variability: Simulation of diversion irrigation" in the Philippines presented that irrigation more than doubles crop-year rice production and income (Rosegrant, 1992). However, because of the dependence of diversion irrigation systems on highly variable dry-season streamflow, irrigated dry-season production, and income are highly variable compared with those of wet-season rain-fed production. This tells us that production & income on a crop-year basis are slightly higher than those that are rain-fed. Although improved management of irrigation systems can reduce expenses and

production disparities among farmers within the system, it has little impact on system-wide variability. Infrastructure and management related to irrigation cannot take the place of other measures, such as buffer stock or import control, that will mitigate the negative consequences of output volatility (Rosegrant, 1992). Besides, the agency in charge of these responsibilities on irrigation, the National Irrigation Administration (NIA), remained the major provider of irrigation as it serviced 955, 653.79 hectares for the national irrigation system while an estimated 737, 402.32 hectares for the communal irrigation system. NIA data also showed that the country's irrigation development status at the end of 2021 is now at 65.28 percent out of the 3.128 million hectares of estimated total irrigable area nationwide (DA, 2022). This means that irrigation in our country is growing and advancing through the platforms that can help the farmers such as the free irrigation service act.

Most other countries charge fees for irrigation, unlike the Philippines which offers free irrigation services. However, Nepal, lying along the southern slopes of the Himalayan mountain ranges in Asia, has high poverty among the farmers and some are due to mediocre land used by marginal farmers and their limited access to agricultural inputs, especially chemical fertilizer, high-yielding seed, and irrigation systems types as well as financing. In light of this, ADB authorized funding in 2010 for the Community Irrigation Project in Nepal for small-scale irrigation projects in 12 districts. This project highlights the goal to promote involvement in irrigation planning, particularly among women, the poor, and other deprived groups in that certain area. This free irrigation in this certain area provided lots of benefits to its people. The production has increased by twofold additionally, farmers were allowed to vary the crops they grew. With these, farmers in the project area increased their income (Ghimire, 2019).

In the meantime, the country's agriculture sector fell by 1.7 percent in 2021, mainly driven by declines in the livestock sector. Corn led the growth with a 28.6 percent increase in production, a reversal of the 18.6 percent decline in the previous quarter. For the entire year, corn production grew 2.1 percent. The Department of Agriculture (DA) pointed out that despite mobility restrictions due to the pandemic and the damage caused by Typhoon Odette, the country's rice production registered an all-time high of 19.96 million metric tons, 3.4 percent more than the previous record of 19.29 million MT (Philstar, 2022).

Unfortunately, rice farmers, whom Filipinos depend on for the bulk of caloric requirements, are among the most disadvantaged in the country. Decades of systemic problems have resulted in a situation where farmers are finding it harder and harder to make a living.

Filipino rice farmers face some serious challenges in the country, high input costs, lack of post-harvest facilities, climate change, market forces, land rent, and demographics (Manila Standard, 2022).

In addition, for moreover recent years, Filipino farmers have been obliged to carry a heavy responsibility to pay fees in exchange for services offered by the National Irrigation Administration. Irrigation Service Fee (ISF) is compensated for water derived from the National Irrigation System (NIS) and Communal Irrigation System (CIS) that the National Irrigation Administration and other government agencies, including those that have been given to Irrigators' Associations (IAs), funded, built, maintained, and managed. For those that are handed to the IAs, operations subsidy is hereby followed which is P 150.00 per hectare and season. On maintenance subsidy, P 1, 750.00 per canal section and per maintenance period (every 45 days, maximum six times in one (1) year (IRR of FISA).

To cease this responsibility, signed on February 2, 2018, RA 10969, or the Free Irrigation Service Act was approved which counts to 5 years of implementation. The program provides that "all farmers with landholdings of eight (8) hectares and below are hereby exempted from paying irrigation service fees (ISF) for water derived. "Farmers with more than eight (8) hectares of land, corporate farms and plantations, drawing water for agricultural crop production; and fishponds and other persons, natural or juridical, drawing water for non-agricultural purposes from NIS and CIS, or using the irrigation systems as drainage facilities, shall continue to be subject to the payment of ISF," the law further states. In addition, the law also condones the unpaid irrigation fees of farmers who own the same size of land. However, in a certain statement of Senator Recto, about the condonation, he uttered that the National Irrigation Administration would not have a negative bearing on waiving irrigation fees. The law even states in the declaration of policy, section 4, that the State to promote comprehensive rural development, food self-sufficiency, equitable access to opportunities, and sustained productivity as key strategies to raise the quality of life in rural areas and attain overall national development. However, while beneficiaries of free irrigation are poorer than average, a large majority of potential beneficiaries are non-poor; to achieve equity objectives, targeted transfers are probably superior to in-kind transfers such as free irrigation.

Exemptions of the law include farmers who own farmlands that exceed eight (8) hectares. Although fish ponds are contributing to agricultural productivity, fish pond owners also pay ISF as irrigation systems were designed particularly for farming purposes. Farmers who are not registered may request the NIA for their inclusion upon presentation of verified proof of the size of landholdings, which must be approved by an authorized irrigation official (Ganancial, 2019).

With the program that provides free ISF, due to fees under the management of the irrigation systems, the farmers are still paying a certain quantity to their respective irrigators' associations. Some also did not yet avail of or applied for the free ISF. Even though the farmers are already using & enjoying the free ISF without availing or applying, the farmers must process the application of their lot to avail FISA. In this way, the farmers are already on the record and can avoid issues that may arise. One is when the administration will no longer acknowledge the free ISF, farmers that are not in the record will continue to pay their past loans or debts. Also, the free ISF can help the farmers save up during the rainy season, two bags of rice or unhusked rice per hectare, and three bags during the dry months to offset expenses (Meniano, 2020). In summary, the farmers can save P 1, 700.00 for the wet season considering a farmland of 1 hectare and P 2, 550.00 for the dry season, giving them a total of P 4, 250.00 per year. This does not deny the fact that farmers are just saving a small amount compared to lavish amounts of expenses due to farm inputs. Another assessment study which was based on secondary data and primary information, adopted strategies such as observation and analysis of poverty and income profile of rice farmers. It also used field experimentation and investigation of the operations. The assessment on this found that free irrigation had the potential to benefit millions of individuals but with small savings in production costs. The analysis showed that despite a significant budgetary allocation for free irrigation, benefits received on a per-hectare or farmer basis are relatively small. Moreover, while rice farmers were inferior to the usual household, most rice farmers were living above the average (Briones et al., 2019). It has then been said from a previous study presented that the program offering free irrigation can provide higher productivity and higher income, but also it does not hide the fact that it cannot affect or give impact to lesser productivity due to crops that prefer rain-fed. Also, investment in irrigation infrastructure and management cannot be a substitute for production instability and importation. These are some of the justifications to highlight the importance of conducting this study.

To preclude issues and disadvantages that may arise through this law, proper implementation must be observed through the implementing rules and regulations. Public programs go through monitoring and evaluation. Monitoring main purpose is to conduct an after the program initiation and during the duration of that program or intervention. Program evaluation on the other side, focuses on the performance of the intervention which determines whether beneficiaries have benefited due to those activities (Kabaghe, 2022). Rule 4 discussed the is the scope of free irrigation which covers landowners of eight (8) hectares and below. Also under this rule, the O&M personnel should keep a registry of the farmers, requirements as proof of their ownership, and those that are exempted who have fishponds and corporate farm owners. Rule 5, discussed the condonation and writing off of loans, past due accounts, and penalties. On Rule 6 were the operation and maintenance of NIS, included also are the subsidies. The technical assistance to Irrigators Associations under Rule 9 was also elaborated.

As what has been mentioned above and by the law of RA 10969, many of the Filipino farmers would benefit from the free ISF hence highlighting the importance of this law, to address some issues regarding FISA and for its better supervision. Given the lesser amount of their cost production, their income will be more focused on the allocation of their farming inputs and labor requirements. Thus, giving the farmers a benefit already that will help them financially. All of the gaps presented above are the shreds of evidence to

conduct this study which will fill the breaks of the previous studies. Therefore, this study would further evaluate the implementation of the Free Irrigation Service Act within the province and how intent it had already reached. This study would also help to direct a strategy to improve the current program.

Research Questions

This research had a chief concern to fill the gaps within the implementation of the Free Irrigation Service Act (RA 10969) in Nueva Vizcaya. Issues may include, not all qualified for the program have made use of the no-cost ISF, the free ISF only led to small savings in production cost, other farmers/FISA beneficiaries were not poor, high farming inputs, and lack of post-harvest facilities, and land rentals. The evaluation targeted to determine the significance of the program and to fill the gap for improvement of the said program with the research questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents?
2. What is the extent of the implementation of the Free Irrigation Service Act?
3. What are the issues and concerns experienced by the farmers about the Free Irrigation Service Act?
4. What are the strategies to improve the implementation of the Free Irrigation Service Act?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used mixed methods with descriptive-evaluative design. The descriptive design used was for determining the profile of the respondents using direct questions. Likert Scale was also adopted as a scale to assess opinions, attitudes, and behaviors. While determining issues, and concerns encountered by the farmers with FISA implementation used an evaluative design using an open-ended question. It is also the same with the key-informant interview. This design helped in drawing exact answers from the respondents, thus, producing a verifiable study.

Participants

This study primarily focused on the three (3) municipalities of the province of Nueva Vizcaya. They were under the National Irrigation System of the Colocol INIS. The system of Colocol was composed of Bayombong, Solano, and Villaverde. In addition, Colocol INIS was the first national system constructed having already finished lined canals and irrigations. The study assessed the Free Irrigation Service Act (RA 10969) which was the basis for strategic direction.

Besides, a key informant interview was conducted. Key Informants were the Operation and Maintenance personnel and Institutional Development Officers from NIA.

Instruments

The questionnaire was used to instigate responses from the respondents selected for the study consisted of three parts.

The first part (A) consisted of questions for the socio-demographic profile to be collected. This part of the questionnaire was intended to elicit information about the sex, age, location, and farm details.

Secondly, (B) was through a Likert scale which contained the dependent variables designed to elicit responses from respondents on the familiarity dimension and to find out the extent to which this affected their quality of life through the Free Irrigation Service Act.

And lastly (C), additional questions were answered with an open-ended result, basically for the recommendations. In designing the questionnaire, the researchers followed the following procedure:

1. Decide what information should be sought;
2. Decide what type of questionnaire should be used;
3. Draft of the questionnaire; and
4. Edit the questionnaire and specify procedures for its use.

As a result, an effort was taken to make sure that the data gathered for instance, on the impact of sufficient motivation on workers' growth and productivity was pertinent to the topic at hand and that the answers given to each question were of the kind that was expected.

Procedure

The data collection procedure started with;

1. Submitted a letter to the respective agency about the purpose of the research and gathered secondary data that may be found in the agency and from other employees.
2. Secondly, upon the consent of the office, the researcher coordinated with involved employees, farmers, and other key informants.

3. Surveyed through questionnaires. Questionnaires were filled out and returned to the researcher in preparation for the next part which was the analysis of results.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the outcomes of the data analysis together with a discussion of the results. It also has four (4) sections, the first is the socio-demographic profile of the farmers. Also, the farm profile is in the second section. The third section contains the results and discussion of the Likert Survey Question. On the other hand, the fourth section is about the discussion of the descriptive part.

Socio-Demographic Profile

Results of the background data of farmers in Bayombong, Villaverde, and Solano, Nueva Vizcaya were obtained from One Hundred Eighty (180) respondents. It was divided into Sixty (60) respondents per municipality.

Out of 180 respondents, 133 were male, and 47 were female. In addition, there were 136 adult respondents and 44 senior citizens. This profiling served as a basis for understanding the characteristics of the population. Hence, knowing the distribution of the demographic characteristics of the respondents aided in determining how closely the sample replicated the population.

Figure 1. Socio-Demographic Profile by Sex and Age

The figure above shows that most of the respondents were composed of male farmers. The profiling resulted in a total of 73.89% male respondents. It then implied that there were men who were more interested in working in the field. As the bodies of men could adapt to more hard work, men can do farming work faster and easier than women. Moreover, a study on the role of men and women in agriculture and agricultural decisions in Vanuatu found that women participated mostly in the production and postharvest activities of food and that men were mostly in the harvesting of food crops (Peralta, 2022).

In terms of age, most farmers were adults which resulted in 75.56%. Adult ages ranged from 25 to 64 years of age. This means that farming work was done by adults more than senior citizens and youth could perform. In addition, a study Aging Farmers Could Add to Food Insecurity, revealed that farmers from 55 years old to 59 years old could contribute to the critical shortage of Philippine farmers in 10 to 12 years (The Manila Times, 2023).

Farm Profile

Profiling of different farm details is beneficial in multiple ways that can capture the realm of agricultural management, sustainable development, and even policy-making.

Crop and Cropping/Year

Results of the farm profile conducted present that a total of 180 respondents dedicated their farming lives to planting rice as their crop. However, out of 180 respondents, an individual was noticed to have another crop besides rice which was corn. Below were figures to present the profiling of the respondents.

Figure 3 above explains that 75.56% of the population crop was rice and 24.44% was dedicated to rice and corn. However, a study says that the top 10 agricultural crops in the Philippines are Sugarcane, Rice, Coconut, Corn, Cassava, Camote, Rubber, and Lanzones (Braganza, 2022). On the number of cropping per year, farmers commonly practiced twice cropping per year.

Number of Hectares

Also, the result showed that 99.44% of farmers practiced farming with two (2) cropping seasons per year (2x/year). Meaning that through the implementation of FISA, most of the farmers were already planting twice a year. However, a study shows that the annual average rice production and rice harvested area totaled among the five Southeast Asian countries were 128.5 Mt and 32.0 M ha, respectively. The Philippines ranked eighth in the world rice production in 2018 (FAOSTAT, 2020). Rice is widely grown in Luzon, Western Visayas, Southern Mindanao, and Central Mindanao. For the past two decades, rice production has increased from 12 Mt in 1999 to 19 Mt in 2008 (FAOSTAT, 2020).

Figure 2. Farm Profile by Crop and Cropping/Year

Figure 3. Farm Profile by Number of Hectares

88.33% of the population’s areas fell from 0.1 hectares to 2 hectares, which were considered small-scale farmers. It just validates the law that beneficiaries must be farmers with farmland with eight (8) hectares and below. These small-scale farmers mentioned above were the farmers who received financial help/subsidy from DSWD (PCO.GOV.PH, September 29, 2023). Secondly, there were about 5% of the population which owned 2.1 to 3 hectares. The least of the population, 1.67% had hectares above 5.

Income per Cropping and Income per Hectare

Meanwhile, Agriculture Assistant Secretary Arnel de Mesa said that President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. has approved the Rice Farmers Financial Assistance program with a budget of P 12.7 Billion. The beneficiaries are farmers who are tilling 2 hectares of land and below and will receive P 5, 000. “And that free seeds have already been distributed – high-yielding varieties both inbred and hybrid fertilizers, machinery to ensure that farmers are ready for the dry season beginning October/November throughout the country,” de Mesa said (Patinio, 2023).

Figure 4. Farm Profile by Income/Cropping & Income/Hectare

The previous profile on areas revealed that most of them owned about 0.1 – 2 hectares which technically meant that they had an income in proportion to their area which fell on P 50, 000 and below. The highest income per cropping was P 50, 000 and below having 57.22% of the population. 17.78% of the population however fell above P 100, 000 as their income per cropping. Moreover, on its income per hectare, 58.89% of the respondents resulted in a P 50, 000 and below income per hectare. Also, 28.33% of the respondents have above P 50, 000 to P 100, 000 income per hectare. And lastly, 12.78% of the respondents said that their income per hectare was above P 100, 000.

Yield in Wet and Dry Season

Additionally, according to the IBON foundation, it was found that the net returns per hectare of rice farmers decreased by about 40% - or from P 32, 976 to P 19, 680, after the rice tarrification was implemented in the year 2019. The drastic loss of income of rice farmers to the tune of P 206 Billion from the rice crisis and from imported rice was estimated by Bantay Bigas (Chi C., 2023).

Figure 5. Farm Profile by Yield during Wet & Dry Season

The yield in the wet season usually had a harvest of more than 50 sacks up to 100 sacks resulting in a 43.33%. 27.78% of the respondents said that they had 50 sacks & below yield. Also, 28.89% of the respondents harvested more than 100 sacks. In addition, according to a journal, the relationships for rainy-season rice production were found to be more complex (Koide et al., 2013). In the dry season, it was higher, which resulted in more than 100 sacks for 49.44% of the respondents. 31.67% of the respondents said that more than 50 sacks up to 100 sacks were their yield. Lastly, a total of 18.89% answered 50 sacks and below. This implies that upon the free irrigation, yield during the dry season went higher. However, it was found in a survey, 1992-1994, that during the dry season, one of its yield losses was characterized by drought (Hossain, M., et al., 1995).

Irrigators' Association

According to the Philippine News Agency, the Philippines has enough rice supply till early 2024 and was assured by the Department of Agriculture (DA) (Patinio, 2023).

Figure 6. Irrigators Association in Colocol INIS

In Bayombong, there were 18.33% recorded as the top respondents, the Lower Addauan IA and the lowest percentage with a total of 15% was composed of Bayag, Bacani, and La Torre North IA. In Villaverde, the top percentage, 16.67% was the Binatawan Nanguyatan Caupligan San Juan IA. However, the lowest percentage was composed of Bintawan Norte Poblacion IA & Sawmill Pieza Villaverde or the Upper Lower Maasin. Lastly, in Solano, the top percentage, 20%, was composed of Magarang Bagahabag Lower Moton IA and the other lowest percentages were the Wacal, Solano Camcam, Roxas Gatafang, Bangaan, and Mapaina Uddiawan IA.

Evaluation of Implementation of FISA

The implementation of free irrigation in the Philippines covered different aspects such as economic impact, environmental impact,

agricultural productivity, social equity, governance, monitoring & evaluation, and also the involvement of stakeholders. Evaluation of the implementation of programs depended on various factors to optimize the policy for the advantage of the agricultural & economic sectors. The evaluation was divided into three (3) parts, Operation & Maintenance, Benefits of FISA, and Technical Assistance to Irrigators' Association. The evaluation focused on the Operation and Maintenance, of how services were rendered to the farmers. While the benefits of FISA evaluated the assistance and guidance provided. Lastly, how these technical assistances to the IAs were rendered.

Operation & Maintenance

In constructing Irrigation Systems, Operation & Maintenance is important in ensuring the effectiveness & sustainability of Agricultural Systems. On the results regarding the implementation of FISA, specifically on Operation & Maintenance, led to a mean of 4.48 and were interpreted as "very beneficial." This means that the execution and upkeep of a system, facility, or equipment have resulted in positive outcomes. These activities contributed positively to various aspects such as efficiency and effectiveness, cost savings, durability of equipment or infrastructure, safety, compliance, customer satisfaction, environmental impact, asset management, and predictive maintenance.

Figure 7. Implementation of FISA on Operations & Maintenance

The above figure revealed that the implementation of the Free Irrigation Service Act on the operation and maintenance had an average of 4.48, equivalent to an interpretation of "very beneficial" which means that farmers were satisfied with the operation and maintenance services of NIA. The most beneficial to them was O and M in Operating Facilities' with an average of 4.63%, this accentuates that O and M personnel did their responsibilities in operating facilities which were very beneficial to the farmers. On the other hand, the lowest percentage of 4.03% fell on farmers having less idea about the "No Irrigated Land Conversion Policy," which was stated in Section 6 of IRR. It encouraged the farmers to sustain gains in irrigation development by discouraging the conversion of agricultural lands. Apart from that, a key informant interview confirmed the result, which also showed that the farmers were satisfied with the program specifically with the free irrigation services offered.

The findings highlighted the importance of operating the facilities in maintaining the free irrigation program as well. Some aspects however needed to be improved such as the Land Conversion Policy.

Benefits of FISA

The provision of irrigation water at no cost to farmers could have potential benefits. With different benefits such as increased agricultural productivity, poverty reduction, drought mitigation, agricultural growth, environmental conservation, social equity, improved livelihoods, and resilience to climate change, the benefits of FISA in the Colocol Integrated National Irrigation System resulted in an overall mean of 4.62 which was "very beneficial" to the farmers. The free irrigation offered to the farmers was known to be very helpful in their livelihood and planting as well. It also helped in farmers' quality of life. Lastly, it also contributed to the strict following of the right cropping calendar. These outcomes showed that the free irrigation offered under this program benefited many aspects not just for its beneficiaries but also for the betterment and enhancement of the program.

On the benefits of FISA, the results indicated that they were 'satisfied,' having a mean of 4.62. It corroborated with the KII results which said that they were satisfied with the benefits of FISA, moreover on the condonation of their debts or backlogs, and that they would not be paying ISF anymore. In connection with that, a study on the Assessment of the Free Irrigation Service Act (Briones R., et al., 2019) resulted in a majority of 87% of respondents saying that the main benefit of FISA was their savings from paying the ISF. It was also seen from the previous study that free irrigation was seen to be beneficial in communal systems, however, it was due to the O and M subsidies and other incentives which were also the same as the KII result of this research study.

Moreover, comparing now and before FISA, 30.38% said that planting now was easier and more comfortable compared to before. 36.71% reiterated that due to FISA, they received higher yields and this served as a big help to their livelihood. 8.86% had said that they experienced better and more continuous water supply. 8.86% have said that they no longer pay and have fewer expenses. And 15.19% fell on other suggestions such as, twice per cropping, additional income, cropping calendar was now followed and more subsidies are given. However, on the KII, they had said that due to FISA, the Irrigators Association became more active, they already

had more funds, additional income to farmers was earned, IAs received operation & maintenance subsidies, and even service areas were corrected. But, on the KII, FISA now resulted in additional work for the NIA personnel regarding this program.

Figure 8. Benefits of FISA

Technical Assistance to Irrigators' Association

Provision of Technical Assistance to Irrigators' Association implicated offering support and guidance concerning technical aspects of irrigation systems, water management, and agricultural practices. It resulted in an overall mean of 4.65 which was "very beneficial" to the farmers. The technical assistance provided included the development of cooperatives, maintaining peace to the IAs, technical assistance and guidance, provision of System Management Committee, dissemination of information to farmers, and making of LIPA.

Figure 9. Implementation of FISA in terms of Technical Assistance to Farmers

Figure 9 explains the technical assistance offered to the farmers. 4.76% of the population had the highest percentage which was about the 'Irrigators' Association being a great help to the farmers." It was then implied that the composition of the Irrigators' Association offered great help to the farmers and was very beneficial to them. In the KII, the data showed that technical assistance offered to farmers was through livelihood training, seminars & workshops which led to additional learning & also income. It also served as a strengthening to their organization. However, the lowest percentage fell on farmers' no idea regarding honoraria received by their IA presidents.

Furthermore, as a result of the KII, technical assistance in terms of reaching every farmer had a often frequency and needed to be addressed. The solution suggested was to create a mobile application to reach the farmers mostly in remote areas. On the dissemination of information, it was also suggested that the IDU or IA representative in disseminating, must consider all ways to reach them. Also, for the farmers to strictly update the LIPA. On the subsidies received by their presidents, farmers had less idea of this.

In an overall assessment, the program reached an average of 4.52 which was 'highly beneficial.' It corresponded to the frequency of "always", it is very important, excellent, almost always true, and had a likelihood of definitely. This means that the program provides significant advantages, positive outcomes, and valuable contributions to its beneficiaries. The operation and maintenance, benefits of FISA, and technical assistance to IAs were highly beneficial. As indicated in NIA's Vision, to provide effective irrigation promoting national development that is inclusive, the program as a result provided "highly beneficial" services in its three (3) areas mentioned above.

However, some areas needed to be enhanced. These were, the intensifying of the "No Irrigated Land Conversion Policy," the technical

assistance to IAs, and making known to them regarding the subsidies received by their respective presidents in exchange for their responsibilities and services rendered.

It was mentioned in the Quality Objectives of NIA that it prioritized the increasing of irrigated areas contributing to Agricultural Productivity, hence, the importance of disseminating about preserving agricultural lands for its purposes. RA 10969, giving free irrigation and at the same time as cited in the declaration of policy, promoting food self-sufficiency. Also, in Section 1 of Article I, according to DAR Administrative Order No. 01-02 of the 2002 Comprehensive Rules on Land Use Conversion, to guarantee food security, the State must protect prime agricultural lands. (DAR,2002), which was in parallel with RA 10969.

It was also found that some farmers were “not highly satisfied” with the technical assistance rendered to them, as well, it was mentioned in the NIA’s Objectives and the importance of the provision of Technical Assistance. As the Agency performs its main objective which is providing irrigation, technical assistance must also be taken into consideration. Having a good partnership with farmers would benefit not just the agency but the whole agricultural productivity and be able to attain the main objective which was to provide an efficient irrigation system.

Also, as per NIA’s Objectives, to provide services in collaboration with farmers and additional local governmental entities, rectifying that IA Presidents received subsidies in exchange for their services rendered to NIA which must be made known to the farmers.

Therefore, with the presented results, it was proven that the program was “very beneficial” but needed to be improved in certain areas, and thus strategic plan was made through this study in patterned with NIA’s Vision, Mission, and Objectives. The agency itself cannot work by itself but is continually in partnership with farmers and other local government units.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the author had reached the following conclusions: Farmers were mostly men and adults. The crops were mostly rice and they planted twice a year. Their income for planting was usually P 50, 000 and below. Their yield for wet was usually above 50 sacks to 100 sacks and for dry season, above 100 sacks.

This study on the experiences of farmers in the implementation of FISA was found to be very beneficial, in terms of Operation & Maintenance, Benefits of FISA, and Technical Assistance to IAs.

The implementation of FISA in the Operation and Maintenance of the National Irrigation System was found to be of great help to the farmers in terms of the services rendered. This included operation, maintenance, and administering of facilities. The alternate wetting & drying followed and the water delivery schedule.

On the Benefits of FISA, it was revealed that the program was of high appreciation for the farmers, it helped the farmers in their livelihood, helped them in their quality of life, and the cropping calendar was followed.

In addition, pointing to the technical assistance given to farmers, results showed that some farmers were not satisfied or were not reached in terms of the technical assistance, but, overall the technical assistance was highly beneficial to them.

With these, some areas needed to be improved through the strategic plan provided. In this way, when strictly implemented, and followed by heart, the services provided to farmers would be extremely beneficial and would aid some issues. It was also helpful that the farmers undergo modernization to cope with change and to be able to participate fully in partnership with NIA and other government agencies.

Hopefully, this research contributed to a wider understanding of FISA, and at the same time, its results, and recommendations can serve as a foundation for future projects and the improvement of FISA.

It was also expected that these results could be used to formulate policies and procedures to advance the program.

Considering the study's outcomes, the researcher recommended the following to the Stakeholders of FISA, to serve as their guide in improving their services, and farming, thus, improving their income. (1) Farmers of Nueva Vizcaya. To the farmers around the jurisdiction of Nueva Vizcaya, that they cooperate with the activities rendered by the National Irrigation Administration through dedication and commitment to NIA to reach the full extent of this program. (2) Irrigators’ Association. (2.1) To the Irrigators’ Association of Nueva Vizcaya, specifically, the presidents, to do their obligations by updating the List of Planted Areas and to contribute to the fast-tracking of this file. Also, the presidents of IAs must double their efforts in reaching farmers through the dissemination of information. (3) Municipal Agricultural Office (3.1) To the Municipal Agricultural Office of the municipalities of Nueva Vizcaya, in partnership with NIA, to render technical assistance to farmers for the modernization of farmers and enhancement of this program. (4) National Irrigation Administration Operation and Maintenance Section (4.1) Personnel must render and follow the correct water delivery schedule to have a better supply of water for the farmers. (4.2) Personnel must ensure that IA presidents do their LIPA. (4.3) The head of the O and M must strictly evaluate the performance of his/her personnel most specifically those on water delivery jobs. (5) Institutional Development Unit (5.1) Provide more quality training/seminars for the farmers. (5.2) Ensure that farmers in remote areas receive seminars/training. (5.3) Ensure the quality of the seminars/training provided to the farmers. (5.4) Use all platforms in reaching farmers and in disseminating information. To give a copy of the important meetings/affairs to the radio station so that remote areas will be reached. Management (5.5) Allocate more training/seminars regarding water delivery schedules to the O

and M personnel including farmers. (6) Future Researchers (6.1) Extend this research to Communal Irrigation Systems (6.2) Consider FISA in terms of its adjacent municipalities (6.3) Conduct a replication of the study for Agricultural College Students since they are exposed to this discipline. (6.4) Research further to determine the difference between FISA in National and Communal Irrigation Systems. (6.5) Research further to include Nueva Vizcaya Bagabag Irrigation System. (6.6) Consider the relationship between FISA implementation and the yield of individual IAs.

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